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THE PREVALENCE AND GEOGRAPHICAL DISTRIBUTION OF THE HELMINTHIASIS IN THE SMALL RUMINANTS IN AZERBAIJAN AND THE PREVENTIVE MEASURES AGAINST THE RISKS

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Abstract

The research works were conducted for the purpose of determining the epizootology of the infection with the helminths and the species composition of the parasites causing the invasion in the small ruminants kept in the livestock farms of the Mountainous Shirvan region of the Azerbaijan. Based on the results of the research work, the helminth fauna of the small ruminants consisted of 43 species of the helminths in the Mountainous Shirvan economic region. 32 species belonging to the class nematodes, 7 species - cestodes, 4 species - trematodes. The larvae of the helminths - *Echinococcus granulosus* belonging to the *Echinococcus* genus and *Taenia ovis* (*Cysticercus ovis*) belonging to the *Taenia* genus of the family Taeniidae from the larval cestodes were noted intensively in the parenchymatous organs.

Keywords: Associative, helminthiasis, larvae, population, incidence coefficient.

Introduction

The special attention is paid to development of the livestock farming for provide the population's demand to the animal meat products in the republic. The parasitic diseases that cause the increase of the productivity, its quality, also the loss of the young animals spread widely in the livestock farms and cause great damage to the country economy as well as the world economy. The helminthiasis are parasitic diseases which caused by different parasitic worms - helminths, are widespread among the agricultural animals. The animals are infected with the helminths mainly in the pastures - in the natural hearths of the helminths. The swamps, the pastures around the wetlands, and the wet meadows are favourable natural hearths for the development of the eggs and larvae of the helminths. In such favorable conditions, the invasion eggs and larvae enter the animal organism through feed and water and infect them. The parasitic worms causing helminthiasis, parasitize by localizing in the organs and tissues of the animals, cause to the reduction of the live weight and productivity in the animals, to the staying the development of the height, to the reduction giving puppies and the quality of the wool, as a result, to the weakening of immunity [5, p.3406-3417; 45, p.61-62]. The temperature, humidity, seasonal changes influence the development of the small ruminants - the growth of the height and weight, the quality of the wool - to the same extent as the helminths. The role of these factors are great also in the formation of helminth fauna in the animals. The researchers have confirmed that the role of the bioecological factors is great in the development of the animals and in the formation of the helminth fauna. Tadesse D, Puchala R, Gipson TA, as well as Papanastasiou DK, Bartzanas T. et al. have confirmed the negative effect of high air temperature to the weight, food demand, respiration and nervous system of sheep in their researches [26, p.6-10; 44, p.492-505]. Habibu B, Kawu M, Makun H. et al. noted that the effect of the season, sex and age on the hematological changes is more active in

tropical goats. They also determined that the gender, reproductive status and number of the fetuses influence the osmotic fragility of the erythrocytes, hematological and physiological parameters in goats in the hot-dry season [17, p.479-490]. The researchers note the widespread distribution of the helminths and helminthiasis among the farm animals and wild animals. They confirmed that 70-100% of the animal populations of the small ruminants are infected by digestive system strongyles and anoplocephalites, 70% by fasciolas, 87% by microceli, and 33% by echinococcal larvae [3, p.23-29; 29, p.108-11; 35, p.8-17]. The rich species diversity of the helminth fauna is particularly attract the attention. And this is related with the anthropogenic and ecological factors. The natural environmental factors and geographic-ecological features of the area influence directly the formation of the parasite fauna of the animals [6, p.694; 24, p.204-220; 31, p. 121-131]. Silva Souza JD, do Santos Difante G. et al. noted that the grazing conditions and Meenakshi Sundaram S, Sivakumar T. et al. noted that the different climatic conditions, relief caused the biometric changes in sheep [22, p.904-907; 38, p. 36-45]. The wide-scale research works have been carried out in the direction of this. The biodiversity of the helminth fauna of the animals depends on the species features, biotic, abiotic, anthropogenic and technogenic factors, as well as regional epizootology features [7, p.86-90; 9, p.763-766; 10, p.321-328]. The Mountainous Shirvan economic region, where research works are conducted, has different characteristics due to the climate, soil cover, relief. The ecological factors also influenced the formation of the helminth fauna in the small ruminants in the region. The location of the Mountainous Shirvan economic regions in the different landscapes - in the plains, foothills, mid-mountains and high mountains influenced directly the formation of the helminth fauna of the small ruminants.

Material and Methods

The research works were conducted for the purpose of determining the epizootology of the infection with the helminths in the small ruminants kept in the livestock farms of the Mountainous Shirvan - Ismailly, Shamakhi, Aghsu and Gobustan economic regions of the republic, and the species composition of the parasites causing the invasion. 1590 sheep and 818 goats from the livestock farms with a migratory and sedentary lifestyle kept in the different relief areas of the research regions were carried out from the helminthological checkup in the spring, summer, autumn and winter seasons. The complete and incomplete autopsy checkups of the animals were carried out [40, p.45-48], the fecal samples were checked by coprological methods - Vishnyauskas, Fulleborn, Berman, Vaida, Darling, Sherbovich [20, p.126-128; 46, p.205]. In order to study the dynamics of the infection with the helminths depending on the season and age, the animals of different ages were researched in each season. The nematodes, cestodes, trematodes, as well as the oribatid ticks, which are their intermediate hosts, also the distribution and species composition of the freshwater molluscs were determined in sheep and goats kept in the individual and farmer livestock farms.

Results

Nematodes

The helminth fauna of the small ruminants kept in the Ismailly-Shamakhi economic regions is different. So in the animals the infection with the nematodes, cestodes and trematodes was noted with the low or high intensity throughout the year.

The nematode fauna of the small ruminants consisted of a total of 32 species of the helminths in the Ismailly-Shamakhi economic regions: *Chabertia ovina*, *Bunostomum trigonocephalum*, *Bunostomum phlebotomum*, *Oesophagostomum venulosum*, *O.columbianum*, *Trichostrongylus axei*, *T.capricola*, *T.colubriformis*, *T.probulurus*, *T.skrjabini*, *T.vitrinus*, *T.asadovi*, *T.ostertagi*, *Ostertagia circumcincta*, *O.trifurcata*, *O.mentulata*, *Marshallagia marshalli*, *Cooperia*

oncophora, *Haemonchus contortus*, *Nematodirus abnormalis*, *N.helvetianus*, *Trichocephalus ovis*, *T.skrjabini*, *Gongylonema pulchrum*, *Dictyocaulus filaria*, *Protostrongylus hobmaieri*, *P.kochi*, *P.davtian*, *P.raillietii*, *P.skrjabini*, *Muellerius capillaris*, *Cystocaulus nigrescens*. The species causing the helminthiasis were identified [15, p.185-233]. The nematodes belonging to the genera *Dictyocaulus*, *Protostrongylus*, *Muellerius*, *Cystocaulus*, *Trichocephalus*, *Chabertia*, *Oesophagostomum*, *Trichostrongylus*, *Ostertagia*, *Marshallagia*, *Cooperia*, *Haemonchus* and *Nematodirus*, which are noted with high intensity and causing helminthiasis were detected in the small ruminants. The intensity of the infection with *Dictyocaulus*, *Protostrongylus*, *Muellerius*, *Cystocaulus* respiratory tract strongylata was 25 - 53 samples (the extensiveness of the invasion – E.I. 65.6%), the intensity of the infection with *Trichocephalus*, *Chabertia*, *Oesophagostomum*, *Trichostrongylus*, *Ostertagia*, *Marshallagia*, *Cooperia*, *Haemonchus*, *Nematodirus* gastrointestinal strongylata was 31 - 252 samples (the extensiveness of the invasion – E.I. 76.8%) in researched sheep. The intensity of the infection with the respiratory tract strongylata was 21 - 48 samples (the extensiveness of the invasion – E.I. 53.8%), the intensity of the infection with the gastrointestinal strongylata was 28 - 166 samples (the extensiveness of the invasion – E.I. 61.5%) in goats. *Chabertia sp.*(length 132.0; width 64.3 um), *Oesophagostomum sp.* (length 77.3; width 47.6 um), *Nematodirus sp.* (length 181.0; width 78.1 um), *Ostertagia sp.*(length 83.1; width 67.9 um), *Haemonchus sp.* (length 78.6; width 47.8 um), *Protostrongylus sp.* (length 89.1; width 68.6 um), *Cooperia sp.* (length 78.5; width 48.7 um), *Trichostrongylus sp.* (length 67.7 width 42.3 um), *Dictyocaulus sp.* (length 88.9; width 49.7 um), *Bunostomum sp.* (length 75.3; width 47,5 um), *Marshallagia sp.* (length 184.4; width 76.4 um), *Trichocephalus sp.* (length 54.3; width 22.5 um) were the most intensively detected nematodes in the checkup of the coprological samples and are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. The nematode eggs detected intensively in the small ruminants (in microscopy). a) *Chabertia ovina*; b) *Oesophagostomum sp.*; c) *Nematodirus sp.*; d) *Ostertagia sp.*; e) *Haemonchus sp.*; f) *Protostrongylus sp.*; g) *Cooperia sp.*; h) *Trichostrongylus sp.*; i) *Dictyocaulus sp.*; j) *Bunostomum sp.*; k) *Marshallagia sp.*; l) *Trichocephalus sp.*

As shown in Table 1, the number of the helminth species belonging to the nematode fauna of the small ruminants, the number of the extensiveness and intensity of the invasion were determined in the Mountainous Shirvan economic regions.

Table 1.

The nematode fauna and prevalence of the small ruminants in the Mountainous Shirvan economic region.

№	Nematode species	Researched small ruminants –2408		I.I., $\bar{M} \pm m$ samples
		infected		
		Samples	%	
1.	<i>Chabertia ovina</i>	1257	52.2	102.4±13.7
2.	<i>Bunostomum trigonocephalum</i>	1197	49.7	87.4±14.5
3.	<i>B.phlebotomum</i>	1088	45.2	79.4±13.1
4.	<i>Oesophagostomum venulosum</i>	1112	46.6	81.8±13.5
5.	<i>O.columbianum</i>	1020	42.4	74.4±12.2
6.	<i>Trichostrongylus axei</i>	1232	51.2	89.7±14.7
7.	<i>T.capricola</i>	1142	47.5	83.14±13.6
8.	<i>T.colubriformis</i>	889	36.9	64.7±10.6
9.	<i>T.probulurus</i>	686	28.5	49.9±8.17
10.	<i>T.skrjabini</i>	484	20.1	35.2±5.7
11.	<i>T.vitrinus</i>	561	23.3	43.6±1.69
12.	<i>T.assadovi</i>	667	27.7	51.8±2.01
13.	<i>Ostertagia ostertagi</i>	1625	67.5	213.5±11.2
14.	<i>O. circumcincta</i>	1391	57.8	182.8±9.6
15.	<i>O.trifurcate</i>	903	37.5	131.4±3.42
16.	<i>O.mentulata</i>	541	22.5	88.4±3.87
17.	<i>Marshallagia marshalli</i>	1598	49.8	126.7±6.6
18.	<i>Cooperia oncophora</i>	1362	56.6	133.4±5.8
19.	<i>Haemonchus contortus</i>	1115	46.3	112.6±8.1
20.	<i>Nematodirus abnormalis</i>	1818	75.5	252±9.52
21.	<i>N.helvetianus</i>	1568	65.2	206.1±10.8
22.	<i>Trichocephalus ovis</i>	1058	43.9	83.9±4.3
23.	<i>T.skrjabini</i>	957	39.7	67.1±2.26
24.	<i>Gongylonema pulchrum</i>	597	14.4	41.8±14.1
25.	<i>Dictyocaulus filaria</i>	1110	46.1	77.7±26.2
26.	<i>Protostrongylus hobmaieri</i>	1229	51.0	46.6±6.94
27.	<i>P.kochi</i>	1053	43.7	39.2±5.9
28.	<i>P.davtian</i>	905	37.6	33.6±5.1
29.	<i>P.raillieti</i>	534	22.2	19.8±0.3
30.	<i>P.skrjabini</i>	484	20.1	17.9±0.27
31.	<i>Muellerius capillaris</i>	960	39.9	35.5±0.53
32.	<i>Cystocaulus nigrescens</i>	1016	42.2	37.5±0.56

From the results of the researches conducted in the highlands, mid-mountains, foothills and plains of the Mountainous Shirvan region, it is known that the infections of the small ruminants kept in the different reliefs with nematodes - strongylates were observed all the year round. The extensiveness and intensity of the infection were noted highly in winter, spring, the first decade of summer and autumn in the mountainous, foothill and plain landscapes. But the infection was observed highly only in the first decade of summer and late autumn in animals kept in the semi-desert type pastures. In all landscapes, the detection of the strongylates which are more characteristic for foothills and plains, is closely related to the nomadic lifestyle of the farms and the biology of the helminths. In the favorable warm and humid climates, the strongylates infect the animals from early spring to late autumn. In the foggy climate in the mountainous areas, the helminth eggs restored their viability, pass to the invasion stage, and they cause re-infection of the

animals with these helminths. The constant presence of the local foci of these helminths is also one of the reasons that sheep are infected with the strongylates in all seasons of the year. It is also considered to be one of the main conditions that these helminths are geohelminths and they pass through the development zone without an intermediate host, reach the invasion stage and infect the animals. But in winter, the animals are kept in the stables or taken out to rich pastures with dirty beds and water ponds around the village. At this time, the helminth cycle continues, it is completed and the re-infection of the animals occurs. The infection of the small ruminants with the nematode is noted in animals of all age groups and in all the seasons. The conducted observations and experiments have shown that in the pastures the development of the nematode eggs and larvae depends not only on general climatic conditions, but also on microclimatic conditions. Whether the eggs and larvae are in feces, in sunny or shady weather, soil or grass, and the time when the eggs

are shed to the pasture are important in the epizootology of the helminth species. So the research scientists studied the biology of the *Trichostrongylus probolurus*, *Tr. axei* and *Tr. colubriformis* species belonging to the *Trichostrongylus* genus have observed that these helminths form larvae even at a temperature of 100 °C, and that the eggs retain their ability to live in the dry feces at room temperature for more than 193 days. The invasive larvae can survive 192 hours in the wet feces and 48 hours in the dry feces at a temperature of 100 °C. Also, the invasion larvae can survive 137 days in the wet soil [2, p.59-67]. Exactly, it has resulted with the properties of the helminths tolerably maintain their viability that they were detected with high intensity in the livestock farms in the unfavorable climatic conditions of both winter and summer. There is information in the literature about the intensive detection of the gastrointestinal strongylates in the agricultural animals in the former CIS states, in all the provinces of Russia. In the Russian Federation - Daghestan Altayev AKh (1959), in Kalmykia Durdusov SD (1995), in the Rostov region Lysenko AA (1972) and Gayvoronsky VI (1980), in Povolzhye Sadov KM (2000), in the Omsk region Bedenkova V N (1986) and Zhidkov AY (1965), in eastern Siberia and the Far East Toshev AP, in the Chuvash Republic Kosyaev NI (2004) have noted the intensity of the infection with the nematodes in the agricultural animals and have conducted wide-scale researches in the direction of the treatment against the diseases [4, p.22; 12, p.p.50; 14, p.29; 33, p.132; 47, p.134-171]. The

infections of the animals with more gastrointestinal strongylates were noted in Australia, Argentina, Pakistan, Africa, Washington and all the countries of the world [30, p. 3-5; p.32, p.176-185; 37, p.64-75; 39, p.31-37; 41, p.277-289; 42, p.489-494].

Trematodes

The *Fasciola hepatica* helminth belonging to the *Fasciola* genus of the *Fasciolidae* family, the *Dicrocoelium lanceatum* helminth belonging to the *Dicrocoelium* genus of the *Dicrocoeliidae* family, and the *Paramphistomum cervi* belonging to the *Paramphistomum* genus of the *Paramphistomatidae* family which are belonging to the *Trematodes* class were detected with high intensity in the mountainous and foothill regions in the small ruminants kept in both sedentary and migratory farms in the Ismailly - Shamakhi economic regions. The extensiveness of the infection with the trematodes was 58.7% in sheep and 48.3% in goats. In the autopsy checkups the intensity of the fasciola and dicroceli helminths collected from the liver was 17 - 85 individuals in sheep and goats. During the research of the coprological samples in the small ruminants, in one view area of the microscope the trematodes were 5 - 7 samples in Aghsu, 7 - 11 samples in Shamakhi, 4 - 9 samples in Ismailly, and 3 - 5 samples in relatively plain areas - Gobustan. The intensity of the paramphistomids collected from the stomach departments was higher in sheep (45 - 96 individuals in sheep, 25 - 37 individuals in goats) and are shown in Figure 2.

Dicrocoelium sp.

Fasciola sp.

Paramphistomum sp.

Figure 2. The trematode eggs in the coprological samples (in microscopy).

The number of the helminth species belonging to the trematode fauna of the small ruminants, the number of the extensiveness and intensity of the invasion are shown in Table 2.

Table 2.

In the Mountainous Shirvan economic region the trematode fauna of the small ruminants and the prevalence according to the seasons.

№	The species of the helminth	Winter – 240 small ruminants		Spring – 240 small ruminants		Summer – 240 small ruminants		Autumn – 240 small ruminants	
		I.E. / %	I.I. $\bar{M} \pm m$ samples	I.E. / %	I.I. $\bar{M} \pm m$ samples	I.E. / %	I.I. $\bar{M} \pm m$ samples	I.E. / %	I.I. $\bar{M} \pm m$ samples
1	<i>F. hepatica</i>	48/20,0	14,8±0,32	60/16,6	12,2±0,12	13/21,6	13,1±0,19	15/25,0	16,2±0,33
2	<i>F. gigantica</i>	16/6,6	7,2±0,13	20/8,3	4,4±0,12	7/11,6	4,3±0,12	8/13,3	4,8±0,13
3	<i>D. lanceatum</i>	192/80,0	251,2±4,27	180/60,0	98,6±2,75	45/70,0	97,2±0,78	50/83,3	132,5±1,56
4	<i>P. cervi</i>	108/45,0	72,5±0,87	12/5,0	22,3±0,37	100/41,6	45,6±0,73	64/43,3	78,4±0,66

In the research area, the trematode fauna of the small ruminants consisted of helminths *Fasciola hepatica*, *F.gigantica*, *Dicrocoelium lanceatum*, *Paramphistomum cervi*. The infection with the helminths was noted in all the landscapes with varying extensiveness and intensity. In the areas of the Mountainous Shirvan economic region, having enough ponds has caused to the population density of the intermediate host molluscs. The intensive distribution of the intermediate hosts, as well as climate and humidity, resulted with the infection of the animals of all age groups of the trematodes in all the seasons of the year. In our researches, in 80% of the animals sick with the trematodoses, the complications - diseases of the secondary infection origin were observed.

The researchers conducting researches in this direction in the Russian Federation have noted that 50 - 93% of the agricultural animals are infected with the trematodes, and the molluscs are the main source of the infection. The researchers pointed out that the diseases are still observed all over the world and cause serious economic damage to the livestock [16, p.508; 28, p.41-69].

Cestodes

In sheep and goats 5 species of the anoplocephalites belonging to the *Cestodes* class: the species from the genus *Moniezia* belonging to the *Anoplocephalidae* family - *Moniezia expansa*, *M.benedeni* and *M.autumnalia*; *T. giardi* belonging to the *Thysaniezia* genus of the *Anoplocephalidae* family

and *A.centripunctata* belonging to the *Avitellina* genus of the *Avitellinidae* family were noted in all age groups of the animals mostly in the spring, summer and autumn seasons. The larvae of the helminths - *Echinococcus granulosus* belonging to the *Echinococcus* genus and *Taenia ovis* (*Cysticercus ovis*) belonging to the *Taenia* genus of the family *Taeniidae* from the larval cestodes were noted intensively in the parenchymatous organs. All these species are parasitize in the small ruminants and are widespread. The imago cestodes were noted in all migratory livestock farms, and that's why no serious zonation was observed in the distribution of the cestodes. In the Mountainous Shirvan economic regions, 1005 sheep from 1590 sheep researched from separate farms were noted as sick with cestodoses (the extensiveness of the invasion 63.2%), *Moniezia expansa* was 66.8%, *Moniezia benedeni* - 52.1%, *Moniezia autumnalia*- 21.6%; *Avitellina centripunctata* - 31.5%; *Thysaniezia giardi* 18.4%. 358 out of 818 researched goats was noted with cestodoses. In goats: *Moniezia expansa* was 54.7%, *Moniezia benedeni* 47.3%, *Moniezia autumnalia* 24.5%, *Avitellina centripunctata* 32.4%, *Thysaniezia giardi* 13.7%. The larval cestodes were determined in 5 sheep out of every 10 sheep and 3 goats out of every 10 goats cut every day for cutting meat. *Echinococcus* (*Echinococcus granulosus*) was detected in the parenchymatous organs (lungs, liver) and invasive protozoocoles were noted in cysticerc bladder fluid of the small ruminants and are shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. The larval cestodes in the parenchymatous organs of sheep.

The number of the species belonging to the cestode fauna of the small ruminants, he number of the extensiveness and intensity of the invasion are shown in Table 3.

Table 3.

The cestode fauna of the small ruminants and the prevalence according to the season

№	The species of the helminth	Winter – 240 small ruminants		Spring – 240 small ruminants		Summer – 240 small ruminants		Autumn – 240 small ruminants	
		I.E. / %	I.I. $\bar{M} \pm m$ samples	I.E. / %	I.I. $\bar{M} \pm m$ samples	I.E. / %	I.I. $\bar{M} \pm m$ samples	I.E. / %	I.I. $\bar{M} \pm m$ samples
1	<i>M. expansa</i>	128/53,3	9,2±0,14	144/60,0	142,2±0,23	120/50,0	7,2±0,13	136/56,6	7,9±0,14
2	<i>M. benedeni</i>	120/50,0	3,8±0,11	64/26,6	43,8±0,45	112/46,6	5,8±0,12	124/51,6	6,2±0,13
3	<i>A. centripunctata</i>	60/15,0	2,3±0,11	72/30,0	34,7±0,42	52/21,6	2,4±0,12	64/26,6	4,6±0,12
5	<i>Th. giardi</i>	48/20,0	2,2±0,11	20/8,3	12,2±0,28	40/16,6	1,3±0,11	44/18,3	2,4±0,11
6	<i>E. granulosus</i>	80/33,3	5,2±0,12	56/23,3	5,8±0,15	92/38,3	5,8±0,12	72/30,0	7,4±0,14
7	<i>Cysticercus ovis</i>	40/16,6	3,5±0,11	24/13,3	2,5±0,11	24/10,0	3,5±0,11	28/11,6	2,4±0,11

Due to the great damage caused by cestodes to the animal husbandry, the helminthological scientists of the world countries are working in this direction. So according to the information of Kurtpinar H. [21, p.51-

55], the *M.expansa* species was widespread among the cattle in Turkey, and the infection intensity of the calves reached 45.2%. In the last decade, it is known

the scientific research works dedicated to the associative infection of sheep with the anoplecephalites and other parasitic worms in Italy [23, p.23-26], the development of the first larval stages of the monesia in Poland [27, p.153-157], the circulation of the monesia in the wild and ruminant animals in nature in Mongolia [36, p.150-156], the role of the oribatid ticks in infection with the anoplecephalites in Japan [34, p.1-6] and Pakistan [19, p.53], the biology of the anoplecephalites and the pathogenesis of the diseases which they cause in India [25, p.119-124], the infection circulation of goats with the anoplecephalites in South Korea [8, p.357-362], the economic damage of the monesia in France [11, p.110-116], the development of the monesia in the last host in the USA [18, p.130-134], and the human [13, p.380-381] infection with *Monesia expansa* in Egypt [8, p.357-362; 11, p.110-116; 13, p.380-381; 18, p.130-134; 19, p. 53; 21, p.51-55; 23, p.23-26; 25, p.119-124; 27, p.153-157; 34, p.1-6; 36, p.150-156].

The cestodes have highly specific adaptations in their distribution in the last and intermediate hosts. Therefore, the spread of these parasites among the small ruminants directly depends on how their intermediate hosts share in the pastures. The American scientists - Stunkard HV, Stol NR, Subias LS confirmed that the development of the monesia proceeds with the participation of the various species of the oribatid ticks [43, p.3-305]. Currently, about 100 species of the oribatid ticks were noted as intermediate hosts of the monesia. 62 species intermediate hosts have been shown for *M.expansa* and 44 species for *M.benedeni* [1, p.28-29]. As a result of our researches, it was determined that 27 species of the intermediate host oribatid ticks, which are included in 7 families, are spread in the pastures of the Mountainous Shirvan economic regions.

So based on the analysis of the research conducted in the Mountainous Shirvan economic region, it can be said that even though these regions are located in the different reliefs, the infections of the animals with the cestodes were observed throughout the year in the Shamakhi, Ismailly, Aghsu regions. The infection with the helminths had a variable character depending on the seasons and relief, and the feature of the foci was observed in some livestock farms. The extensiveness and intensity of the infection were noted, albeit weakly, in the foothills and plains landscapes. This is due to the nomadic lifestyle of the small ruminants and the fact that the amount of the precipitation is higher than the annual norm in the recent years, the favorable conditions create for the development of the intermediate hosts.

The helminth fauna of the small ruminants has a rich feature from the relief of the region, from the influence of the geographical-ecological, abiotic and biological factors in the Mountainous Shirvan economic region. So the biology and epizootology of the helminths also play a special role as the main factor in the formation of the helminth fauna. The infection situation of the small ruminants with the helminths was different according to the seasons and landscapes and these are shown in Figure 4.

In the plain landscapes (Gobustan), the small ruminants were infected with 36 species of the helminths (32 species of the nematodes, 2 species of the trematodes, 2 species of the cestodes), and the infection situation has changed according to the seasons. In winter, the extensiveness of the invasion was noted 55.4%, the intensity of the invasion 15.3 - 195.7 samples. In spring E.I. was noted 72.6%, I.I. 23.1-284.6 samples; in summer 56.9%, 9.5 - 143.6 samples, in autumn 69.0%, 12.4 - 227.5 samples.

In the foothill landscapes (Aghsu), the small ruminants were infected with 39 species of the helminths, 32 species of the nematodes, 3 species of the trematodes and 4 species of the cestodes were characteristic. In winter, the extensiveness of the invasion was determined 35.7%, the intensity of the invasion 14.8 - 153.2 samples; in spring E.I. - 85.4%, I.I. - 25.5 - 298.6 samples; in summer E.I. - 61.7%, I.I. - 21.4 - 144.3 samples; in autumn 79.3%, I.I. - 26.4 - 285.3 samples.

The infection with 38 species of the helminths (28 species of nematodes, 4 species of trematodes, 6 species of cestodes) was noted in the small ruminants kept in the Ismailly, Shamakhi regions, located in the mountainous landscapes at an altitude of 2000 m above the sea level. In the Ismayilli district in winter E.I. was noted - 42.0%, I.I - 11.3 - 39.2 samples; in spring E.I. - 67.7%, I.I. - 29.0 - 198 samples; in summer E.I. - 56.7%, I.I. - 17.8 - 154.1 samples; in autumn 68.4%, I.I. - 27.5 - 224.3 samples. In the Shamakhi region, in the winter season the extensiveness of the invasion was 48.0%, the intensity of the invasion 9 - 31.8 samples; in spring E.I. - 77.3 0%; I.I. - 35.4 - 225.0 samples; in summer 64.8%, I.I. - 25.7 - 176.4 samples; in autumn 72.2% , I.I. - 45 - 224.5 samples.

In the small ruminants the infection with the helminths was noted in an associative form (nematodes, cestodes, trematodes) in the winter, spring, summer and autumn seasons and these are shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. The infection dynamics of the small ruminants with the helminths by landscapes.

The *Fasciola hepatica*, *Dicrocoelium lanceatum*, *Paramphistomum cervi*, *Echinococcus granulosus*, *Cysticercus ovis*, *Moniezia expansa*, *M.benedeni*, *Bunostomum trigonocephalum*, *Chabertia ovina*, *Oesophagostomum venulosum*, *Cooperia oncophora*, *Ostertagia ostertagi*, *Marshallagia marshalli*, *Trichostrongylus axei*, *Haemonchus contortus*, *Nematodirus abnormalis*, *Dictyocaulus filaria*, *Protostrongylus hobmaieri*, *Muellerius capillaris* helminths were the dominant species in the associative form of the infection.

Based on the results of the research work, the helminth fauna of the small ruminants consisted of 45 species of the helminths in the Mountainous Shirvan economic region. 32 species of these species belonging to the class nematodes, 7 species - cestodes, and 4 species - trematodes. 8 species of the helminth fauna were zoonanthropous helminths - *F.hepatica*, *F. gigantea*, *D.lanceatum*, *E.granulosus*, *T.axei*, *T.vitrinus*, *H.contortus*, *G.pulchrum*.

Discussion

So, according to the analysis of the research works carried out in the separate regions of the Mountainous Shirvan, it can be said that although these regions are located in the different reliefs, the infections of the small ruminants with the helminths were observed throughout the year. The infection was detected with the different intensity in all the seasons. In recent years, the rainy weather and high humidity affected positively the development of the nematodes in the pastures, and have created conditions for them always staying in the invasion condition. And such favorable conditions cause the nematode infection of the sheep kept in both sedentary and migratory farms all the year round. In different foci, the wide spread of the fasciola, dicroceli and paramphistomum helminths causes the intensive infection of the small ruminants with the trematodoses in the research regions. The infection of the animals with the cestodes is noted with higher intensity in the mountainous and foothill areas. And it is explained by the presence of the favorable conditions in the region for the development of the oribatid ticks, which are intermediate hosts in the spread of the anoplosecephalites. The infection with the larval cestodes from the

dogs and wild animals due to by not conducting in time the dehelminthization measures in farm dogs, as well as from non-compliance the sanitary and hygienic rules in the farm area. In the region, the reason of the infection of the small ruminants with the helminthiasis is the relief, climate, humidity of the region and direct influence of the other environmental factors. The infection with the helminths has a variable character depending on the seasons and relief, and the foci feature was observed in some livestock farms. The extensiveness of the infection was relatively high in the mountainous areas, and weak in the regions covering the foothills and lowlands. The anoplocephalites, which are more characteristic for the mountainous areas, were also detected in the animals kept in the foothill and plain regions. And this is due to the migratory lifestyle of the small ruminants and the fact that in recent years, the amount of the rainfall is higher than the annual norm, the creating favorable conditions for the development of the intermediate hosts.

Conclusion

Taking into account the high incidence coefficient and incidence risk of the infections with the helminthiasis in the small ruminants, a plan of the preventive measures was prepared for the Mountainous Shirvan region.

- The small ruminants should be regularly dehelminthization, for this, first of all, should be conducted a coprological checkup in the animals, and the infected animals should not be allowed to the pasture. The contents of the dehelminthized animals should be burned or buried;

- In the Mountainous Shirvan ecological-geographical regions the infection with the helminthiasis varies depending on the season of the year, so dehelminthization measures should be carried out 4 times a year starting from the last months of the winter season, because the infection occurs at the end of winter and early summer in the plain areas, and at the end of spring and early summer in the mountainous and foothill areas. In the migratory farms, the animals must be dehelminthized before migration. The shepherd dogs which are in the farm should also be dehelminthized 4 times a year;

- In order to increase the resistance of the animals against the infections with the invasive larvae and eggs of the helminths, it is important to feed them with full-quality feeds, which are rich in vitamins A, C, B₁₂, macro and micro elements with the physiological requirements;

- The grazing of the animals is expedient away from water areas, ponds, as well as in the pastures consisting of plants - wormwood, camelthorn, prangos, etc., which have an anthelmintic effect;

- In order to destroy the intermediate hosts of the helminths (molluscs, earth mites and other invertebrates), the stagnant waters, watery, swampy areas should be drained, the quality of the pastures should be improved, the young and old animals should be grazed in the separate pastures;

- Alternating pastures should be created in all the livestock farms, the animals should be grazed alternately in those pastures for 7 - 10 days. At this time, the helminth cycle is disrupted and the reinvasion is prevented (for example, the moniesia eggs and larvae perish in 3 - 5 days if they do not find their intermediate hosts - oribatid ticks in the external environment);

- In each livestock farm, the artificial pastures should be created, the perennial plants (trefoil, oat, etc.) should be planted, and the newborn animals should be grazed there for 20 - 30 days until the immunity is strengthened;

- The slaughtering of the animals must be provided only in the special slaughterhouses. In the individual farms, pasture camps and migration routes, the animal slaughtering should be specially controlled, the liver, lung and other organs infected with the echinococcal cysts should be burned or buried deeply;

- Before giving the manure of the agricultural animals to the fields, gardens and melons, the helminth eggs should be destroyed in the environment, the manure should be neutralized thermally for prevent their spread;

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Conflict of interest

There is no conflicts of interest.

References

1. Andreeva M.V. The monieziosis in cattle. Mater. 2nd Intern. Correspondence scientific-practical. conf. "Agrarian education: history, problems, prospects", Yakutsk, 2005. pp. 28-29
2. Asadov SM. The distribution of the helminths of the ruminants in the ecological zones of the Azerbaijan USSR. Ceskoelouenska parasitologic.1959. TVI-l.g. pp. 59-67.
3. Ataev AM. The epizootic situation on the animal parasitosis in Daghestan / A.M. Ataev. Veterinary; 2002. №4. pp. 23-29.
4. Bedenkova VN. The features of the epizootology of the gastrointestinal nematodes in cattle and measures to combat them in the beef farms in the Non-Chernozem zone of the RSFSR. Author's abstract. cand. diss. M., 1986. 22 pp.

5. Benjamin L. Hart Behavioural defences in animals against pathogens and parasites: parallels with the pillars of medicine in humans. *Philos Trans R Soc Lond B Biol Sci.* 2011 Dec 12; 366(1583): 3406–3417. doi: 10.1098/rstb.2011.0092

6. Carnovale F, Phillips CJC. The Effects of Heat Stress on Sheep Welfare during Live Export Voyages from Australia to the Middle East. *Animals* 2020; 10: 694 10.3390/ani10040694 [PMC free article] [PubMed] [CrossRef] [Google Scholar]

7. Chinnamani K, Kumar VRS, Muralidharan J, Thiruvankadan AK, Sivakumar K, Ramesh V. Growth, production and reproduction performance of Salem black goats under intensive and semi-intensive systems of management in Tamil Nadu. *J Ent. Zool. Stud.* 2018; 6: 86–90. [Google Scholar]

8. Cho Kwang-Hyun, Lee Ji-Hong, Kim Dae-Jung, Kim, Seung-Joon, Kwon Oh-Deog, Kwak Dong-Mi. Infection rate of parasites from feces of Korean indigenous goats in northern areas of Gyeongbuk province. *Korean Journal of Veterinary Service*, 2008, vol. 31, issue 3, pp. 357-362.

9. Dass G. Production performance and management practices of Pugal sheep in the home tract. *Ind J Anim. Sci.* 2007; 77: 763–766. [Google Scholar]

10. David I. Gibson, Rodney A. Bray, David Hunt, Boyko B. Georgiev, Tomaš Scholz, Philip D. Harris, Tor A. Bakke, Teresa Pojmanska, Katarzyna Niewiadomska, Aneta Kostadinova, Vasyl Tkach, Odile Bain, Marie-Claude Durette-Desset, Lynda Gibbons, František Moravec, Annie Petter, Zlatka M. Dimitrova, Kurt Buchmann, E. Tellervo Valtonen, Yde de Jong. *Biodivers Data J.* 2014; (2): e1060. Published online 2014 Sep 17. doi: 10.3897/BDJ.2.e1060 PMID: PMC4206782 Fauna Europaea: Helminths (Animal Parasitic)

11. Dorchies P. Moniezia expansa: importance du parasitisme, consequences economiques. *Revue De Medecine Veterinaire*, 2009, v. 60(2) pp. 110-116.

12. Durdusov SD. The ecological and epizootological characteristics of the main helminthiasis and coccidiosis of cattle and measures to combat them in the arid zone of southern Russia. Abstract of the dissertation for the degree of Doc.Sciences, S-P. 1995. 50 pp.

13. El-Shazly AM, Morsy TA, Dawoud HA. Human Monieziasis expansa: the first Egyptian parastic zoonosis. *J. Egypt. Soc. Parasitol.*, 2004, vol. 34, No 2, pp. 380-381.

14. Gaivoronsky VI. The epizootology of the strongylatoses of the digestive tract of sheep in the specialized sheep farms and industrial feedlots. Autoref. diss. cand. veterinary sciences, M., 1980. 29 pp.

15. Gibbons LM, Khalil LF. A key for the identification of genera of the nematode family Trichostrongylidae Leiper, 1912. *Journal of Helminthology*; 1982. pp. 185-233. <http://doi.org/10.1017/S0022149X00034581>

16. Gorokhov VV. The epizootic process in fascioliasis and the biological basis for the regulation of the number of mollusks - intermediate hosts in the prevention of helminthiasis. Abstract of the dissertation for the degree of Doctor of Biological Sciences. M., 1986. 508 pp.

17. Habibu B, Kawu MU, Makun HJ, Aluwong T, Yaqub LS, Ahmad MS et al. Influence of sex, reproductive status and foetal number on erythrocyte osmotic fragility, haematological and physiologic parameters in goats during the hot-dry season. *Vet Med.* 2014; 59: 479–490. [Google Scholar]
18. Jankovska I, Vadlejch I, Szakova J, Miholova J, Kunc D, Knizkova P, Cadkova I, Langrova I. Experimental studies of the cestode *Moniezia expansa* (Cestoda: Anoplocephalidae) in its final host (*Ovis aries*). *Experimental Parasitology*, 2010, vol 126; No 2, pp. 130-134.
19. Khosa S. Observation on oribatid mites as vectors of cestode parasites on pastures around Tandojam (Pakistan). Tandojam, Sindh Agriculture Univ., 2006, 53 pp.
20. Kotelnikov GA. The helminthological researches of the animals and the environment. Moscow; 1984. pp.126-128.
21. Kurtpinar X. The parasitic diseases of the domestic animals in Turkey and measures to combat them / Mater. 4th International Region, Conf. countries of Asia on the parasite. disease. *Animals. M.*, 1959. pp. 51-55.
22. Meenakshi Sundaram S, Sivakumar T, Ramesh V, Gnanaraj PT. Comparative performance of Madras Red Sheep under different management systems. *Ind J Anim Sci.* 2002; 72: 904–907. [Google Scholar]
23. Moazeni M. Mixed infection with intestinal tape worms in sheep. *Trop Biomed.*, 2004, vol. 21 (2), pp. 23-26.
24. Munoz CA, Campbell AJD, Hemsworth PH, Doyle RE. Evaluating the welfare of extensively managed sheep. *PLoS ONE* 2019; 14(6): e0218603 10.1371/journal.pone.0218603 [PMC free article] [PubMed] [CrossRef] [Google Scholar]
25. Narsapur VS. Pathogenesis and biology of Anoplocephaline cestodes of domestic animals. *Annales de Recherches Veterinaires*, 2008, vol. 29(1) pp. 119-12.
26. Papanastasiou DK, Bartzanas T. Relation between potential sheep heat-stress and meteorological conditions. International conference on Agricultural Engineering. AgEng 2014. Zurich, 6–10 July. <http://www.geysecos.es/geysecos/adjs/comunicaciones/304/C06280001.pdf>.
27. Polec W, Moskwa B. Development of early larval forms of *Moniezia expansa* under laboratory conditions. *Wiadomosci Parazytologiczne*, 2004, 50(2), pp. 153- 157.
28. Popov NK. Fascioliasis in the foothills of the North Ossetian and Chechen-Ingush Autonomous Soviet Socialist Republics. North - Ossetian state. *ped. int.* 1941. pp. 41-69.
29. Popov MA. The influence on the helminthological situation of the type of the feeding and the method of keeping sheep in the conditions of complexes. MA Popov. *Tr. VIGIS.* 1975. V. 17. pp. 108-111.
30. Qayyum M. Some epidemiological aspects of gastrointestinal strongyles (Nematodes: Strongyliodea) of sheep in the subtropical zone of Pakistan. Ph.D. Thesis, Quid-i- Azam University, Islamabad-Pakistan. 1996.
31. Reddy PRK, Kumar BR, Prasad CS, Seshiah CV, Hyder I. Erythrocyte fragility based assessment of true thermal resilience in tropical small ruminants. *Biol. Rhythm Res.* 2019.10.1080/09291016.2018.1447353 [CrossRef] [Google Scholar]
32. Reinecke RK and Louw JP. Overberg Research Projects I: The epidemiology of parasitic nematodes in ewes, suckling lamb and weaners. *J. South African Vet. Assoc.*, 1989. 60: 176-185.
33. Sadov KM. The strongylatoses of the gastrointestinal tract of cattle in the Middle Volga region. *Diss. vet. Sciences.* Ivanovo, 2000. 132 pp.
34. Satoshi S. Oribatid mites (Acari: Oribatida) as an intermediate host of Anoplocephalid cestodes in Japan. *Applied Entomology and Zoology*, 2004, vol. 39, № 1, pp. 1-6.
35. Scasta JD. Livestock parasite management on high-elevation rangelands: ecological interactions of climate, habitat, and wildlife. *J Integr Pest Manag.* 2015; 6: 8-17.
36. Scharhun G, Sharkhun T. The helminthfauna of wild and domestic ruminants in Mongolia - a review. *Eur. Wildlife Res.*, 2004, vol. 50, № 3, pp. 150-156.
37. Siddiqi MN and Ashraf M. Helminthiasis in goat slaughtered in the abattoirs of Peshwar, NWFP. *Pakistan J. Agri. Res.*, 1980. 1: 64-75.
38. Silva Souza JD, do Santos Difante G, Neto JVE, Lana AMQ, da Silva Roberto FF, Ribeiro PHC. Biometric measurements of Santa Inês meat sheep reared on *Brachiaria brizantha* pastures in Northeast Brazil. *PLoS ONE* 2019; 14(7): e0219343 10.1371/journal.pone.0219343 [PMC free article] [PubMed] [CrossRef] [Google Scholar]
39. Singh D, Swarnkar CP, Khan FA, Srivastava CP and Bhagwan PSK. Epidemiology of ovine gastrointestinal nematodes at an organized farm in Rajasthan, India. *Small Ruminant Research*, 1997. 26(1-2): 31-37.
40. Skryabin KI. The method of the complete helminthological autopsy of the vertebrates, including humans. Moscow: Moscow State University; 1928. 45pp.
41. Southcott W H, Major GW and Barger I.A. Seasonal pasture contamination and availability of nematodes for grazing sheep. *Australian J. Agri. Res.*, 1976. 27: 277-289.
42. Suar V H and Busetti MR. The epidemiology of helminth infections of growing sheep in Argentina's Western Pampas. *Int. J. Parasitol.*, 1995. 25: 489-494.
43. Subias LS. Listado sistematico, sinonimico y biogeografico de los acaros oribatidos (Acariformes, Oribatida) del mundo (1758-2002). *Graellsia*, 2004, vol. 60(extra. 1), pp. 3-305.
44. Tadesse D, Puchala R, Gipson TA, Arthur L, Goetsch. Effects of high heat load conditions on body weight, feed intake, temperature, and respiration of Dorper, Katahdin, and St. Croix sheep. *J Appl. Anim. Res.* 2019; 47: 492–505. 10.1080/09712119.2019.1674658 [CrossRef] [Google Scholar]

45. Taylor R.J. The eating behavior and helminthic diseases. *br. J. Anim. Behavior* 2 1954. pp. 61–62. 10.1016/S0950-5601(54)80033-5 (doi:10.1016/S0950-5601(54)80033-5) [CrossRef] [Google Scholar]

46. Thienpoint D. Diagnosing Helminthiasis through Coprological Examination. Janssen Research Foundation, Beerse, Belgium, 1979.

47. Toshchev AP. The helminth fauna of the domestic animals of the Eastern Siberia. *Tr. Irkut. NIVS.* 1949. Issue 1. pp. 134-171.